

**Spectrophotometric Determination of
Niobium through Heteropoly Blue Formation**

U. MURALIKRISHNA* and J. ADINARAYANA MURTY

Department of Chemistry, A. U. P. G. Centre,
Nuzvid-521 201

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC methods for the determination of niobium involving the formation of molybdenum blue are very few^{1,2}. In these methods molybdoniobophosphoric acid (MNPA) is reduced to heteropoly blue after the selective extraction or decomposition of the excess of binary

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molybdophosphoric acid (MPA). The methods reported need strict adherence to the experimental conditions. In the present investigation, conditions have been established for the spectrophotometric determination of niobium through the formation of the ternary heteropoly acid, MNPA. It is not possible to form MNPA in aqueous solutions without the simultaneous formation of MPA. MPA is selectively extracted² by isobutyl acetate. Subsequently, the MNPA complex in aqueous phase is reduced with ascorbic acid at the suitable acidity to molybdenum blue. The method is relatively free from time restrictions, simple, sensitive and is applicable to the estimation of niobium in steel samples.

Experimental

A stock solution of niobium was prepared by fusing Nb_2O_5 (0.143 g; G. R., Loba) with potassium pyrosulphate (~1.5 g) and the fused mass was dissolved in water and made upto 100 ml. The niobium content was checked gravimetrically with 8-hydroxyquinoline³. Working standard solution was made by appropriate dilution. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure: Aliquots containing 25–200 μg of niobium were taken in different 25 ml volumetric flasks, each containing 5 *N* sulphuric acid (2.5 ml), 4% ammonium molybdate (2.5 ml), phosphate solution (2 ml; 0.1 mg P/ml) and water to make upto 15 ml and then allowed to react for 15 min for the complete formation of MNPA. The contents were extracted with isobutyl acetate (10 ml) and the organic layer (upper layer) was discarded. The extraction was repeated twice. To the aqueous phase, were added 5 *N* sulphuric acid (7.5 ml) and 5% ascorbic acid (2 ml) and then heated on a water-bath for 15 min. The solution was then cooled and made upto 25 ml and absorbance was measured at 820 nm against the reagent blank. The reduced complex, so obtained, exhibited steady absorbance even after 24 h.

Results and Discussion

Niobium (as niobate) reacts with MPA to form the ternary complex, molybdoniobophosphoric acid (MNPA). This ternary complex may be reduced to molybdenum blue and the reduced product exhibits maximum absorption at 820 nm. The acidity during the formation of MNPA may be varied from 0.5 to 1 *N* (sulphuric acid) and the optimum is found to be 0.8 *N*. But for the reduction, the optimum acidity was found to be 2 *N* (sulphuric acid). Acidity lower than 1.5 *N* gives intense coloured blank due to reduction of free molybdic acid and above 2.5 *N* it requires prolonged heating. The optimum concentrations of molybdate, phosphate and ascorbic acid are fixed at 2.5 ml of 4%, 2 ml of 0.1 mg P/ml solution and 2 ml of 5% solution

respectively. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $1.68 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 4.8 ng cm^{-2} respectively.

Nitrate, chloride, acetate, citrate, sulphate, silicate, copper, manganese, magnesium, cadmium and nickel do not interfere in the determination upto 100-fold excess, whereas tantalum, oxalate, tartrate and fluoride interfere.

An appropriate size of sample consistent with Nb content was prepared⁴ from the steel samples. The results (average of 5 determinations) are as follows (certified values in parenthesis): sample no. 1, 0.051 ± 0.009 (0.05), no. 2, 0.059 ± 0.011 (0.06) and no. 3, $1.080 \pm 0.009\%$ (1.06%).

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